

STUDIES IN HYDROGEN BOND FORMATION.

PART II. ALCOHOLS

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In continuation of the work on amides, the association characteristics of methyl and ethyl alcohols and phenol have been investigated. The changes in association are followed by the changes observed in the C-O frequency under different conditions of temperature and solution in polar and non-polar solvents. The observed difference in the behaviour of the alcohols in solutions of water, as compared to that of the amides, has been explained as due to the difference in the types of polymers formed.

In continuation of the author's work on the molecular association of amides (*Science & Culture*, 1941, 6, 509; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 337) the association characteristics of the alcohols have been studied by the use of Raman effect, a short report of which has already appeared (*Science & Culture*, 1944, 9, 302). The alcohols chosen for study are methyl and ethyl alcohols and phenol.

In respect of physico-chemical properties, alcohols like water show highly abnormal properties. In Ramsay and Shield's equation for the surface tension of the liquids the value of K and X for methyl and ethyl alcohols are 0.93 and 3.4; and 1.08 and 2.75 respectively as against 2.10 and 1.01 for normal liquids. The corresponding value for the association factor for phenol is 1.43. If these divergences are to be taken as an indication of the degree of molecular association, these liquids ought to be highly associated, particularly the methyl and ethyl alcohols.

The association in alcohols has been largely investigated in the infra-red region. These investigations have been concerned with the changes observed in the intensity and frequency of the absorption band of the hydroxyl group occurring at 3700 cm^{-1} (2.70μ) and 3400 cm^{-1} (2.94μ). The band at 2.70μ is ascribed to the C-H vibration of the isolated single molecules and that at 2.94μ to the associational O-H. Errera and Mollet (*Compt. rend.*, 1937, 204, 257) found that in very dilute solutions of aliphatic alcohols in CCl_4 and CS_2 the absorption band at 2.70μ characteristic of single molecules is observed while the one at 2.9μ tends to disappear. Increase of temperature is found to increase the intensity of the 2.70μ band and to decrease that of 2.94μ . Observations on the absorption of the vapour support this view. Similar evidence for vapour like molecules of alcohol in CCl_4 solutions was reported by Kinsey and Ellis (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, 5, 399), Freymann (*Compt. rend.*, 1937, 204, 41), Buswell and Rodebush (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, 5, 501). On the other hand, Errera and Sack (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, 34, 728) explained the association of alcohols in CCl_4 or CS_2 by the formation of double molecules and complexes of higher order, the latter vanishing rapidly with increase of temperature. The effect of solution of alcohols in oxygenated solvents like ether, acetone, nitrobenzene and

dioxane was studied by Gordy (*Phys. Rev.*, 1935, 50, 1161; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 605), Freymann (*loc. cit.*), Badger and Bauer (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, 5, 839), Errera and Sack (*loc. cit.*). The observed changes in the intensity and frequency of the vibration band of the C-H of the alcohol were explained as due to the formation of a weak inter-molecular hydrogen bond between the oxygenated compound and the alcohol.

The association in phenol like that of the alcohols has been mainly investigated in the infra-red region. Naherniac (*Compt. rend.*, 1932, 195, 1254) reported that phenol in the fused state has a wide absorption band with intensity maximum at 9853Å which shifts to 9776Å with increase of temperature. Brattain (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1938, 6, 298) studied the effect of temperature on phenol and observed a small shift on the 3.1 μ band from solid to liquid phenol which was further shifted at higher temperatures. From the small changes observed he concluded that the degree of association has not been appreciably changed. Evidence for the decrease of molecular association of phenol in solutions of carbon tetrachloride has been presented by Naherniac (*loc. cit.*), Freymann (*loc. cit.*), Fox and Martin (*Nature*, 1937, 139, 507). The effect of solution of phenol in oxygenated solvents was studied in infra-red by Gordy and Nielsen (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1938, 6, 12) who reported the formation of weak additive compounds by sharing the proton of the OH group. Huggins (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1936, 1, 407) cited evidence for the existence of weak additive compounds between phenols and ketones and between phenols and cyclic ethers which he attributed to hydrogen bridges.

From the Raman effect point of view the association in alcohols has been meagrely studied. Meyer (*Physikal. Z.*, 1931, 32, 293) reported that there is no difference between the spectrum of pure methyl or ethyl alcohol and that of a mixture of alcohol and CCl₄. Krishnamurty (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1931, 6, 401) reported that the only change that was observed in the spectrum of methyl alcohol in solutions of water is the shift of the C-O frequency at 1030 to lower values which he attributed to the formation of hydrates. Landsberg and Ukholin (*Compt. rend. U.S.S.R.*, 1937, 16, 391) studied methyl alcohol both in the liquid and the vapour state and found that the O-H band at 3400 shifts to 3680 which is ascribed to that of an unassociated O-H group. The association in phenol has not been studied at all. Only the different investigators (*Monatsh.*, 1929, 52, 379; *Indian J. Phys.*, 1929, 4, 196; *Sci. Paper. Inst. Phys. Chem. Res. Tokyo*, 1929, 11, 205; *Z. physikal. Chem.*; 1929, 48, 299) who worked with phenol contented themselves with a study of the pure substance at the laboratory temperature and a record is made of the number of Raman lines observed.

EXPERIMENTAL

It is evident from the foregoing summary, that not much work has been done from Raman effect point of view to understand the association characteristics of the alcohols. Hence, a systematic investigation of these was undertaken by the author. The alcohols were investigated at tem-

peratures of 5°, 30° and 60° (in the case of methyl alcohol) and 75° (in the case of ethyl alcohol). Phenol was investigated in the solid and liquid state and at 135°. The effect of solution in polar solvents like water, and non-polar solvents such as benzene and CCl_4 was studied. The effect of solution in an oxygenated solvent, acetone, was also investigated. Mixtures with ether could not be studied owing to the presence of an ether line 1028 close to the C—O line in the alcohols. Study of solutions of alcohol in nitrobenzene presents a similar difficulty. The method of purification of the liquids and the general experimental technique employed is described in detail elsewhere (*loc. cit.*).

Methyl Alcohol.

Raman Frequencies of Methyl alcohol.—This liquid has been studied by many investigators and there seems to be a general agreement between their results. The mean values of the various frequencies as given by Kohlrausch ("Der Smekal-Raman effekt" 1931, p. 309) are :

$$\Delta\nu = 1034 \text{ (5), } 1362 \text{ (0), } 1462 \text{ (5b), } \\ 2836 \text{ (6b), } 2943 \text{ (5b), } 3378 \text{ 85 Band.}$$

Besides these, Ganesan and Venkataswaran (*loc. cit.*) have reported a line at 1257. It is probable that both the lines 1257 and 1362 are the C—H lines excited by 4078Å of the mercury arc. The Raman frequencies of methyl alcohol as measured by the author are as follows :

$$\Delta\nu = 1032 \text{ (6), } 1446 \text{ (4b), } 2832 \text{ (10b), } \\ 2928 \text{ (8b), } 2943 \text{ (5b), } 3378 \text{ (Band)}$$

Of these the line at 1032 is well known to be due to the C—O oscillation ; 1446 corresponds to the CH_2 vibration. 2832 and 2928 are the valence C—H lines. The band at 3378 with a width of 430 cm^{-1} arises out of the O—H group in the alcohol.

Frequency Changes in Solution.—The changes observed in methyl alcohol lines due to solution in the various solvents are described below.

- (i) *Non-polar*—Benzene and carbon tetrachloride have no effect either on the intensity or frequency of the Raman lines of methyl alcohol. This is in agreement with that reported by Meyer (*loc. cit.*).
- (ii) *Polar and Normal*—Among the normal polar solvents used with advantage, is acetone. In mixtures of alcohol and acetone the 1032 line which is ascribed to C—O oscillation in methyl alcohol shifts perceptibly to the lower frequency.
- (iii) *Polar and Abnormal*—Water, which belongs to this class of substances, brought about prominent changes in the C—O frequency, 1032, of methyl alcohol. Three concentrations were studied ; 100%, 75% and 25% by volume. The 1032 line is definitely shifted towards smaller frequencies (*cf.* Fig.

1 & 2). The shift is progressive, the maximum being in the lowest dilution where the 1032 line has shifted to 1010. The other lines remained more or less unaffected. It was not possible to study the effect of water on the O-H band of the alcohol due to the superposition of the water band on the alcohol O-H band.

Effect of Temperature.—Methyl alcohol was studied at 5°, 30°, and 70°. No prominent changes have been observed in the C-O line at 1032. The effect of increase in temperature on the O-H band, excited by the 3650 group of Hg lines, of methyl alcohol is perceptible (*cf.* Fig. 3). The intensity maximum of the band at 3378 cm^{-1} at 5° shifts to 3438 cm^{-1} at 30° and this is not further changed at 60°. The width of the band which is about 430 cm^{-1} remains the same at all the temperatures investigated. The absence of any change in the intensity maximum of the band with increase of temperature from 30°–70° can be regarded as an evidence that the degree of association has not been appreciably changed. The shift of this band to lower frequencies in the spectrum taken at 5° indicates that it may be due to further association through hydrogen bonding.

Ethyl Alcohol

Raman Frequencies of Ethyl alcohol.—This liquid has been studied by many investigators, the most comprehensive one being that of Bolla (*Z. Physik*, 1934, 89, 513; 1934, 90, 607) who observed 56 frequencies of which 42 are combinational leaving 14 fundamental frequencies. There seems to be a fair agreement between the results reported by the various authors, and the mean values as given by Kohlrausch (*loc. cit.*) are:—

42 (1), 888 (5), 1046 (3),
1094 (1), 1273 (1), 1456 (4b),
2876 (6b), 2928 (7b), 2974 (5).

It is probable that the 1094 line owes its origin to 4046 excitation and is really the C-H line of frequency 2876. The Raman frequencies of ethyl alcohol as measured by the author are as follows:—

428 (1), 898 (6), 1052 (4),
1274 (2), 1455 (4b), 2874 (7b),
2929 (10b), 2958 (7), 3978 (Band).

In the case of the first member of the series of alcohols the assignment of the various frequencies to the different oscillations did not present much difficulty. But in the case of ethyl alcohol there seems to be a divergence of opinion between the assignments made to the different frequencies. This could be easily understood as the force constants of the C-OH and the C-C are very nearly the same, as the mass of the hydroxyl group differs from that of a methyl group by only two units.

Hibben ("The Raman Effect and its Chemical Application", p. 143) and the various other workers on the Raman spectrum of ethyl alcohol ascribe the 886 line to the C-O and the 1052 line to the C-C oscillations. The argument advanced in support of this is, that the C-C frequency in the corresponding hydrocarbon ethane is $\Delta\nu$, 993 and from the correspondence of this to the 1032 of methyl alcohol and as the frequency is generally supposed to decrease with increasing chain length, the 885 frequency occurring in ethyl alcohol has been ascribed to the C-O oscillation. But it is surprising, if the assignment is correct, why there should be such a marked shift of the C-O frequency of 1032 in methyl to 886 in ethyl alcohol. On the other hand, Venkataswaran and Bhagavantam (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1930, 5, 129), Canals and Gastaud (*Bull. soc. chim*, 1937, 4, 2042) on the basis of polarisation measurements, assign the partially polarised line near 1052 as due to the C-O. The changes observed by the author in solutions of water lend support to this assignment. It is difficult to conceive how the changes can be observed in the C-C oscillation (1052 according to the assignment of other workers) without at the same time noticing any changes whatsoever in the C-O oscillation (886 according to the assignment of other workers).

Hence, the author is inclined to think that the 886 is the C-C and the 1052 is the C-O frequencies in ethyl alcohol.

1455 is the δ (C-H) frequency and the three lines occurring at 2874, 2929, 2958 are due to the valence C-H oscillations. The O-H bond for ethyl alcohol occurs with an intensity maximum at 3378 cm^{-1} .

Frequency changes in Solution.—As far as the author is aware, this is the first systematic attempt to study ethyl alcohol in the various solvents. The changes observed in ethyl alcohol lines under the different conditions studied are described below :

(i) *Non-polar.*—Benzene and carbon tetrachloride have no effect either on the intensity or frequency of the Raman lines of ethyl alcohol.

(ii) *Polar and Normal.*—As in the case of methyl alcohol only mixtures of acetone and ethyl alcohol were investigated. The 1052 in ethyl alcohol shifts slightly to lower frequencies. No prominent changes have been observed in other lines. The complementary effect of ethyl alcohol on the acetone lines is more marked as observed by the frequency shifts of C-O of acetone.

(iii) *Polar and Abnormal.*—Water, which belongs to this class of substances brought about conspicuous changes. Three concentrations were studied—100, 75 and 25%. Taking the lines one after another their assignments together with the changes observed are given below :

(i) $\Delta\nu$ —886 (C-C). No change is observed either in the intensity or frequency of this line.

(ii) $\Delta\nu$ —1052 (C-O). This line shifts to lower frequencies, the shift being 6 cm^{-1} .

(iii) $\Delta\nu$ —1455 (C-H). This line shifts appreciably to higher frequency.

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

O-H band of MeOH at diff. temp.
Fig. 3

EtOH at diff temp.
Fig. 5.

4916

C-H lines $\Delta\nu = 886$
EtOH-H₂O mixture
Fig. 4.

(iv) $\Delta\nu=1274$. This line becomes diffuse and broad and tends to disappear both on dilutions and at increased temperatures.

(v) $\Delta\nu=2874, 2929, 2958$ (C-H). A very marked shift is observed in these lines (*cf.* Fig. 4.). With dilution there is a progressive shift of these lines towards higher Raman frequencies, the maximum shift observed in the lowest dilution is 30 cm^{-1} .

Effect of Temperature.—Ethyl alcohol was studied at 5° , 30° , and 80° . No prominent changes have been observed in any of the lines. The effect of increase of temperature on the O-H band in ethyl alcohol is perceptible. The intensity maximum of the band at 3378 cm^{-1} at 30° shifts to 3403 cm^{-1} at 75° (*cf.* Fig. 5). The width of the band, which is about 360 cm^{-1} , remains unaltered at all the temperatures investigated.

Phenol

Phenol was purified by repeated distillation under vacuum and the experimental technique employed is described in detail previously (*loc. cit.*). The Raman spectrum of the substance could be obtained in 10 hours by the author. The various Raman frequencies observed are given in Table I. Since some of the faint lines observed by the author have also been previously observed by Ganesan and Venkateswaram (*loc. cit.*) but not included in the tabulated values as given by Kohlrausch (*loc. cit.*), they are given in column I of Table I for purposes of comparison. Column II contains the values as given by Kohlrausch. In column III are given the Raman frequencies as measured by the author for solid and liquid phenol. Many new frequencies (noted with asteriks) have been observed.

TABLE I
Raman frequencies of phenol.

I Ganesan & Venkateswaram.	II Kohlrausch	IV Author	
		III Solid	Liquid
	235 (2)	248	230 (2)
	526 (2)	530	425* (1b)
816	614 (2)	620	530 (4)
769	758 (1)	760	620 (4)
819	813 (3b)	822	822 (7b)
			908* (1)
			914* (1)
1007	1002 (5)	1000	1000 (10)
	1024 (3)	1020	1025 (8)
			1085* (2)
1178	1170 (3)		1155 (5)
		1245	1245 (4b)
1369			1375 (1)
1496		1490	1496 (2)
1604	1598 (3)		1605 (5)
1860	2059 (5b)		2080 (10b)
3388			

The line at $\Delta\nu=1000$ is the C-C frequency and the 1025 line is the C-O frequency. The line at 3060 is the valence C-H. Many of the other lines are those that arise from the benzene ring.

Frequency changes in Phenol at different Temperatures.

Solid-Liquid.—The frequency changes observed are as follows:—

(*v*) $\Delta\nu=230$. This shifts slightly to lower frequency, the shift being 8 cm^{-1} .

(*ii*) $\Delta\nu=822$. This line which is diffuse in solid is quite sharp in liquid.

Liquid, 30°–135°. More perceptible changes were observed at higher temperature and the intensity and frequency changes of the various Raman lines are discussed below :

(*i*) $\Delta\nu=760$. This is the feeble component accompanying the 822 line and tends to disappear at the higher temperature.

(*ii*) $\Delta\nu=1025$. This diminishes considerably in intensity and shifts slightly to higher frequency with increase of temperature and the maximum shift observed at 135° is 5 cm^{-1} .

Frequency changes in Solution.—The changes observed in phenol lines due to solution in the various solvents are described below:—

Non-polar.—Carbon tetrachloride has no influence either on the intensity or frequency of the Raman lines of phenol.

Polar and Normal.—Among the normal polar solvents studied is acetone. In mixtures of acetone and phenol, the 1025 line, which is ascribed to the C—O oscillations, shifts perceptibly to lower frequency. Besides this, one of the low frequency lines, $\Delta\nu=620$, shifts slightly to lower frequency.

Polar and Abnormal.—Water is the prominent member which belongs to this class of substances. Unlike methyl and ethyl alcohols, which are miscible in all proportions, phenol forms with water what are called "Conjugate solutions" and it is only above the consolute temperature, which is 68.4° , that phenol and water are mutually soluble in all proportions and the system consists of but one liquid phase. Hence, solutions of phenol in water were studied at 80° . Great difficulty was experienced in the study of these solutions as they were getting coloured after a few hours' exposure to ultraviolet light and exhibited strong fluorescence. The only concentration which could be successfully studied was 10% by weight of phenol. The aqueous solution which exhibited strong fluorescence was purified by the method adopted previously in the case of sugars (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1940, 14, 207) and amides (*loc. cit.*) by treatment with carbon. A combination of two filters consisting of sodium nitrite solution and iodine in carbon tetrachloride was used to photograph the Raman spectrum.

The following are the main changes that have been observed :

$\Delta\nu=230, 530, 629, 760$. These are the low frequency lines which are probably due to intermolecular oscillations. All these lines are too feeble to be noticeable in solutions of water.

$\Delta\nu=1025$ (C—O). No perceptible shift is observed in this line. The only changes that could be observed is the marked decrease in intensity, a change analogous to what has been observed with increase of temperature.

$\Delta\nu=1245$. This line shifts to lower frequencies, the shift being 10 cm^{-1} .

DISCUSSION

It has been suggested that the alcohols, phenols and water form associated chains as

where the oxygen of the hydroxyl group acts as the donor and the hydrogen as the acceptor. Sidgwick ("Electronic Theory of Valency", 1929, pp. 134, 149; *Chem. Rev.*, 1937, 20, 259) suggested that this chain is not likely to contain more than 3 or 4 molecules. In the case of water, it is known with certainty* from both the X-ray and Raman effect data, that it is associated to triple molecules. In alcohols, the evidence (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1934, 2, 73) from the data on heats of mixing and the X-ray data of Zacharisen (*ibid.*, 1935, 3, 158) point to the existence of double molecules. But there is other evidence from infra-red data, and the results obtained by Wulf (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, 33, 179) on the heats of dilution of alcohols, indicate the possibility of more complex grouping than double molecules. In solutions of water, which is of high dielectric constant, the tendency is to dissociate. This has been shown to be the case in amides by the author (*loc. cit.*). Koteswaram (*Z. Physik*, 1938 110, 118; 1939, 112, 395) reported similar results in fatty acids. The conclusions arrived at in those substances were based on the changes observed in the C-O frequency. Hence they are definite. It is only in the case of alcohols where there is only C-O that it is found necessary to depend on the changes observed in this frequency.

In aqueous solutions of methyl alcohol, it was found that the C-O line at 1032 shifts progressively to lower frequencies with increased dilution. This is an anomalous result with what has been observed in amides and acids. The difference in behaviour can be explained as follows. In the case of acids, which form closed ring complexes, the dimer structure has to be broken down first before any change can take place. It has been reported by Koteswaram (*loc. cit.*) that even at the largest dilutions there is no trace of evidence for the combination of water molecules with the acid molecules. In the case of alcohols, which form open chain compounds, a 'donor' and an 'acceptor' are both exposed at either end of the chain. Hence, the effect of solution in water may be that even without the breaking up of the polymer, the water can associate with the alcohol through the formation of a hydrogen bond. Hence, it is, that a shift of the 1032 line to the lower frequencies has been noticed. This is in agreement with the results obtained in infra-red by Gordy (*loc. cit.*) and by Krishnamurthy (*loc. cit.*) in Raman effect. A similar shift in the C-O line of ethyl alcohol has also been noticed, though this is not as prominent as that observed in methyl alcohol.

*There is an alternative hypothesis of the quasicrystalline structure of water first proposed by Bernal and Fowler (*J. Chem. Phys.* 1933, 1, 515).

Meyer (*loc. cit.*) reported that in solutions of methyl alcohol and water a line scarcely visible in the pure alcohol gets clearer as more water is added. It may be that this new line is nothing but the C—O line. As Meyer has taken the spectrum of methyl alcohol with unfiltered mercury arc and probably with a small dispersion instrument, this line in pure alcohol might have been masked by the C—H lines excited by the 4046 group of mercury lines which come very close to it. At larger dilutions in water, it shifts to lower frequencies and increases in intensity with increasing dilutions, and hence is more easily detected than the line in pure alcohol

Another very interesting change has been observed in the case of ethyl alcohol. The C—H lines shift prominently towards the higher frequencies, while the C—O line shifts to lower frequencies and no perceptible change is observed in the C—C line.

If the above were to represent the structure of ethyl alcohol, in solutions of water the C—O bond weakens due to association with water molecules and consequently the rest of the molecule, enclosed by the dotted line, gets strengthened. Hence it is, that a change towards higher frequencies of the C—H lines is noticed. It is surprising that no similar change is observed in the C—C binding. Besides these changes, the deformation frequencies undergo prominent shifts.

The change of temperature from 5° to 70°C brought no changes in the C—O line or any of the other lines thereby showing, that in the temperature range investigated, the degree of association has not appreciably changed. The effect of temperature on the O—H bands in the alcohols is perceptible. Similar conclusions were arrived at by Badger and Bauer (*loc. cit.*) who report the absence of a sharp O—H band in methyl alcohol even at 71°. But they, however, report that it is quite evident in ethyl alcohol.

The line $\Delta\nu=822$, which is diffuse in solid phenol, is sharp in liquid phenol which indicates depolymerisation. The feeble component 760 of the 822 line disappears at the higher temperature. It is likely that the 760 line might be due to the polymers which are present at the laboratory temperature. The slight shift of the 1025 line to higher frequencies from solid phenol to liquid phenol at 135° indicates that the degree of association has not been very much changed. Besides these, the deformation frequency occurring at 1405 undergoes a shift to the higher frequency. The changes observed in solutions of water seem to indicate depolymerisation. The low frequency lines which are characteristic of the intermolecular oscillations disappear in solutions of water thereby showing that water, which is a high dielectric, decreases the polymerisation of

phenol and hence the lines, which are characteristic of associated groups, disappear. This observation is dissimilar to what has been noted in the aliphatic alcohols, but is in agreement with the general phenomenon occurring in other associated substances (e.g., acids, amides.)

Besides this, the 620 line shifts to lower frequency. It has been previously shown by Koteswaram (*loc. cit.*) in acetic acid and by the author (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1929, 14, 365) in glycerine that this line is susceptible to changes in association.

The slight shift to the lower frequencies of the C—O line in the alcohols and in phenol in solutions of acetone, indicates that a weak intermolecular hydrogen bond had been formed between the hydroxyl group of the alcohol and the keto oxygen, as

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